

European network to promote grazing and to support grazing-based farms on their economic and ecologic performances as well as on animal welfare

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Contributors

Name	Organisation
Giovanni Peratoner	Laimburg
Lisa Fracchetti	Laimburg
Arno Krause	GLZ
Manfred Kayser	UGOE
Agnes van den Pol-van Dasselaar	Aeres
Deirdre Hennessy	Teagasc
Mugur Jitea	USAMV

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Context Analysis
CP	Context Profile
FA	Facilitator Agent
G4AE	Grazing4AgroEcology
STWG	Scientific & Technical Working Group

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1 Introduction

This document is part of T3.2 (Conducting Context Analysis improving transferability & spreading of best practices) within Grazing4Agroecology and contains guidelines to perform a Context Analysis of innovative practices implemented by grazing-based farming systems in an agroecological perspective. Context analysis is a process that combines best practices with scientific knowledge to enhance the transferability and adoption of innovations, thus providing a tool making the dissemination and application of innovations more efficient. An innovation will only be an innovation and have a positive impact where it fits. We believe that innovations and new ideas should be evaluated to narrow to environments in which they might be applied. This would greatly increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the process. The Context Analysis is meant to provide a link between the innovator and the wider farming community. In order to make things work there should be a certain 'degree of identity' between the 'sender' and potential 'receivers'. In this sense, the 'sender' is the innovation in the context of origin and the receiving end is the environment which is supposed to be improved through implementing this innovation. The degree of identity is what must be assessed to allow for a successful transfer.

1.1 Role of the Scientific & Technical Working Group (STWG)

The Scientific & Technical Working Group (STWG) is an international panel of experts working for the project Grazing4AgroEcology (G4AE). It is composed by scientists and national experts, being at least one per project partner (≥ 18 persons in total), but not limited to. Invited experts may complement the STWG depending on the specific case under examination.

Among others, the STWG plays a major role in G4AE in synthesising, validating, and enriching the capital tapped in WP2 in form of narrative and case-specific information with know-how improving the transferability of innovations/best practices to contexts differing from that of origin, called Context Analysis.

To improve its efficiency, the work concerning the Context Analysis will be performed by three sub-groups, each one led by a sub-group leader (Agnes van den Pol-van Dasselaar (AVDP), Giovanni Peratoner (GP), Mugur Jitea (M)).

Regular meetings (as many as necessary – as few as possible) will be held, but in general:

- one meeting per month per sub-group is expected on average (especially in the first year of the project);
- entire group meetings (when necessary and on demand) will be organised to exchange experiences and to harmonize processes and approaches;
- (paper-) work between meetings will be needed for the preparation of the meetings and the review of results;
- flexibility and pro-active participation will be key elements for an effective work.

2 Performance of the Context analysis and preparation of the Context Profiles

2.1 Information basis needed for the Context Analysis

For each best practice case (120 in total), a practice abstract and a short video (T2.3) will be provided to the sub-group to perform the Context Analysis. These items will be the narrative to be further processed by the STWG.

Data, relevant to the innovation, will be collected at farm level (T2.2 and T2.3). Some important remarks with respect to the data collection are:

- Data will be collected by means of a first visit questionnaire in the form of an Excel tool. A less structured narrative, reflecting the mindset of the farmers, will also be collected as the basis for the description of the innovation in the context of the farmers farming system, which will flow into the practice abstract and the 2 minutes video.
- The variables/questions addressed in the questionnaire include information readily available to the farmers and provide relevant and reliable information for the Context Analysis.
- All farm data collected should be relevant to the reference year 2022 and be an average/sum over the whole year. An exception is the cost benefit analysis, where the information should be relative to the system in place before the innovation was introduced.
- Some sections are obligatory, other are addressed only if relevant (see the first visit questionnaire for details).

2.2 Contents of the Context Profiles

The results of the Context Analysis will be compiled in a Context Profile, resulting in 120 Context Profiles, which will feed into T3.4 (national grazing-AKIS meetings).

The Context Profile is a complement to the practice abstract, the practice video and the first visit questionnaire and it aims at evaluating the transferability of an innovation from the context of origin to the European context.

Some contents are directly obtained from activities performed in T2.2 and T2.3, others are the result of activities of the STWG (Table 1).

Table 1. Contents foreseen by the project proposal and their implementation through actions performed in other tasks and by the STWG.

Contents foreseen by the project proposal	Action	Source
Analysis, synthesis and enrichment with scientific knowledge	Fact checking, validation and request for integrations to the first visit questionnaire (if needed), add relevant literature	Information material from best practice cases (T2.3), expertise of STWG
Identification of specific needs, challenges and opportunities	Context Analysis in the context of origin (pre-defined categories allowing for a data base search → for instance EU-FarmBook)	First visit questionnaire (T2.3)
	Context Analysis in the context of origin (descriptive)	First visit questionnaire (T2.3)
	Extension of the Context Analysis to the European context according to agroclimatic zones	Information material from best practice cases (T2.3), expertise of STWG
Barriers to adoption	Identification of implementation gaps and research gaps according to agroclimatic zones	Information material from best practice cases (T3.2), expertise of STWG
Suggestions to adapt	Identification of adaptations according to agroclimatic zones	Information material from best practice cases (T3.2), expertise of STWG
Cost-benefit analysis	Cost-benefit analysis in the context of origin	First visit questionnaire (T3.2)

2.3 Performance of the Context Analysis

The Context Analysis is performed with the support of an evaluation matrix provided in Excel format (see Table 2).

Table 2. Template of the evaluation matrix.

Case study code: xx	Agro-climatic zone								
	Alpine	Atlantic central	Atlantic north	Atlantic south	Boreal	Continental north	Continental south	Mediterranean north	Mediterranean south
Item 1									
Item 2									
Item 3									
Item 4									
Item ...									
Implementation gaps									
Suggestions to adapt									
Research gaps									
Literature									

very limited transferability	
generic information/not relevant	

The agroclimatic zones are defined according to the PESETA-Agriculture study:
https://images.slideplayer.com/37/10730127/slides/slide_4.jpg (Figure 1).

Iglesias, A., Garrote, L., Quiroga, S., Moneo, M.: Impacts of climate change in agriculture in Europe. PESETA-Agriculture study. EUR 24107 EN; DOI 10.2791/33218; EC

Figure 1. Agroclimatic zones according to the PESETA-Agriculture study.

These zones are meant not only to represent the climatic conditions, but also, to a certain extent, cultural and socioeconomic conditions within that geographic area.

The Context Analysis is performed by means of the following steps:

1. Classify each best practice case according to a set of pre-defined terms within categories, addressing i.e. the main domain of the innovation, the agroclimatic and soil conditions. This is the prerequisite for conducting an efficient and effective database search in the database of choice. At the present time the integration of the best-practice information into EU-FarmBook (<https://eufarmbook.eu/>) is under examination. This database allows farmers to quickly and easily find best practice cases that are relevant to their context. The responsibility for classifying the best practice cases lies with the project partner who prepares the practice abstract, video, and first visit questionnaire. Once the best practice cases are classified, they are validated by the STWG. The final choice about the categories and the keywords within the categories will be made once their compatibility with the database has been ascertained. See Appendix 1. for a first provisional draft.
2. Identify some key innovation elements from the information material provided: these are elements of the innovation needed to be assessed to evaluate the transferability of the innovation to other agroclimatic zones. They can be:
 - o Elements of the classification performed under point 1;
 - o In general prerequisites (what must be done in order for the innovation to be implemented), strengths (main positive effects expected) or weaknesses (main drawbacks expected if the innovation is implemented);
 - o Facts/information derived by any section of the first visit questionnaire (e.g.: amount of water used for irrigation → water for irrigation must be available to a low price);

- Elements of the innovation analysis from the first visit questionnaire (as they have already been stated).

For the definition of these key elements, the following hints can be useful:

- Try to define a short list of items (4-5) with the aim in mind not to try to go into detail, but to concentrate on items making sense in an international assessment and providing useful information to farmers over a range of different contexts. It is clear that the Context Analysis has a certain margin of subjectivity. For this reason, attention must be paid to concentrate on general transversal/overarching topics, worth and capable to be assessed also in other contexts.
- Concentrate on items:
 - Which can be expressed in a concrete, numerical form (e.g. at least a certain number of grazing days/year). These are those which can be most objectively assessed;
 - representing the main strengths of the innovation in an agroecological perspective (e.g. forage autonomy/no off-farm purchase of concentrates);
 - representing prerequisites/needs which can be assessed in an international context (e.g. a certain amount of water, expressed in mm per year or in mm needed during the growing season would make more sense to be assessed than a need for irrigation, as the irrigation need could possibly apply only to regions having water scarcity and not being relevant in other regions);
- A general formulation of the item is necessary to allow for a meaningful evaluation (i.e. 'forage autonomy' better than 'produce enough hay for the winter').
- 3. Assessment for each cell in the matrix (key innovation elements × agroclimatic zone) **the transferability, i.e. the possibility to implement the respective element and the probability of occurrence of the expected effect**, according to a simple colour system:
 - a. Green: strong transferability;
 - b. Yellow: slightly limited transferability;
 - c. Red: very limited transferability;
 - d. Grey: generic information/not relevant.
- 4. Input **implementation gaps** (infrastructural and socioeconomic gaps), if any. These gaps refer to infrastructural and socioeconomic gaps that could hinder the adoption of the innovation in different contexts. For instance, lack of access to technology, inadequate infrastructure (e.g. inadequate water supply or inadequate farm roads), or limited financial resources could prevent farmers from adopting the innovation.
- 5. Input **research gaps** (knowledge gaps to be bridged by research activities), if any.
- 6. Input **suggestions to adapt** (possible changes to the innovation/farm system making it fit for other contexts), if any. These suggestions could include possible changes to the innovation or farm system that would make it more suitable for adoption in different areas. For instance, changing the size of the farm or modifying the technology used could increase the feasibility of adoption in other contexts.
- 7. Input **Literature**: the primary target audience are farmers and advisors, but scientists should not necessarily be excluded; ideally the provided references are technical reports having sound scientific research in the background, but papers can also be possibly included. The list should be limited to few (max. 3-5) relevant sources.

With the exception of step 1, all steps are going to be performed by the members of the sub-group of the STWG working at the specific Context Profile.

3 Organisation of work

The Context Analysis is performed by the STWG by processing the information gathered within the frame of WP2. In order to reduce the workload of the single STWG members and to improve the efficiency, the analysis of the single best practice cases is performed by sub-groups.

3.1 Choice of case-specific composition of the sub-groups

The Context Analysis of each best practice case is conducted by a sub-group of the STWG (6 members of STWG).

The composition of the sub-group will be case-specific and will be determined ad hoc for each best practice case, aiming at maximising the interaction of all project STWG members.

The sub-group will consist of:

- one of the sub-group leaders (AVDP or MJ or GP);
- five other members of the STWG fulfilling, as far as possible, the following criteria:
 - o the practice partner of G4AE who proposed the best practice case under study and being the link to the case study (able to provide additional information needed for the context analysis); further persons providing information for the analysis of a specific best practice case can be integrated ad hoc into the sub-group, also if they are not officially part of the STWG;
 - o member(s) of the STWG with theoretical and with practical expertise on the main domain/topic of innovation of the best practice case;
 - o members of the STWG from the same geographical area and from different geographical areas to provide different point of views on the transferability of the best practice example in terms of climatic and/or socioeconomic conditions.

In general, a certain balance between science and practice will be aimed at.

3.2 Workflow for assignment of tasks and collection of results

1. Each project partner is responsible for transmitting the information material (practice abstract, video, first visit questionnaire) produced within T2.3 and the classification of the best practice case according to the predefined set of categories and keywords to the Task leader (send them to lisa.fracchetti@laimburg.it). An updated inventory of the progress and a repository of the information material is organised on an online platform accessible by all STWG members.
2. As soon as the information material of case studies are complete, the information material needed to perform the Context Analysis is provided to the members of the selected sub-group in advance, possibly as a bundle of cases to be assessed in one round.
3. The co-ordinator of the sub-group arranges tasks to be performed by its members and the timetable for completing the work. These tasks include the validation of the information material and the classification for database search, the draft of the key elements of the innovation, the evaluation of the transferability, as well as the completion of all other elements of the context profile. If additional information is needed, clarifications or improvement suggestions are requested to the project partner who provided the information material.

3.4 Further improvements

The guidelines in this report represent a support for the start of the conduction of the Context Analyses, but adaptations and refinements are expected, wherever meaningful and useful, as further practice experience will be gained by the STWG after the analysis of the first set of best practice cases.

4 Appendix

Appendix 1. Provisional list of pre-defined categories and keywords within categories for the evaluation of the innovation.

Main domain of the innovation
improvement of grassland management
animal management
workload reduction
improvement of plant protection
improvement of nutrient cycle
breeding advance
improvement of marketing
Agroclimatic area
Alpine
Atlantic central
Atlantic north
Atlantic south
Boreal
Continental north
Continental south
Mediterranean north
Mediterranean south
Climate
very high rainfall
moderate rainfall
little rainfall
mild winter
Soil type
sand
loam
peat
clay
Management
pasture dairy
pasture beef
cutting-only
ley farming
Technical
difficult
easy
computer-based
Finance/investment
low
mid
high
Market
global
local - urban
local - rural
Social
full-time farmer
part-time farmer
hobby

